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Grid Impact Assessment of High Power E-Bus Charging Methods with Seasonal Load Variations

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Abstract

The ongoing electrification of public road transport helps to significantly reduce greenhouse gas emissions and increase the local air quality. Besides financial and operational challenges during this process, the high electric power demand for charging e-buses raises questions about potential impacts on the local distribution grid. This work addresses these questions by modeling several types of e-bus charging behavior in a representative European city and performing grid simulations with seasonal load variations at a high time resolution. The results show that charging at the end stations of the bus line caused smaller voltage drops at the grid than charging at every station. Moreover, the increased energy consumption of e-buses and households in winter led to a higher grid loading than in summer. To conclude, the presented simulation approach has proven to be an adequate method for assessing grid impacts of charging e-buses and will be used for future research.

Keywords: grid integration; e-bus; electric vehicle; EV; heavy-duty

1. Introduction

In 2016, road transport accounted for 19.5 % of the total EU greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions (European Environment Agency, 2018). In this context, the electrification of urban public transport, mainly regarding buses, is considered as an essential method to significantly reduce the global emissions as defined in the 2015 Paris-Agreement on climate action (United Nations, 2015). Studies show that an introduction of battery electric buses (BEBs) in city transit networks can reduce CO₂ emissions. When taking into account the current EU electricity mix, reductions of 41 - 51 % can be expected for this mode of transportation (Mohamed et al., 2016; Xylia et al., 2017).

Furthermore, the electrification of city buses can greatly reduce the emission of toxic air pollutants. For the city of Rome, Valenti et al., 2017, investigated a prospective public transport scenario with a fleet battery electric bus percentage of 30 % compared to existing 0 %. The comparison reveals that in the future scenario, the local air quality significantly improves: The emission reduction amounts 37 % for nitrogen oxides (NO_x), 36 % for carbon monoxide (CO), 33 % for hydrocarbons (HC) and 50 % for particulate matter (PM).

However, the integration of large BEB fleets into existing bus networks is a complex and expensive task. In this context, accommodating the variety of operational demands, achieving environmental benefits and being economically feasible are often considered as the main challenges for the introduction of public e-buses (Zhou et al., 2015; Miles & Potter, 2014).

A crucial aspect which must be kept in mind when switching from internal combustion engine buses to BEBs is the grid integration of the necessary charging infrastructure. For electric passenger vehicles, various existing studies focus on the grid impacts of coordinated and uncoordinated charging (Mwasilu et al., 2014; García-Villalobos et al., 2014). A widely accepted consensus in this regard is that low voltage grids will be the first to suffer from simultaneously charging electric vehicles (International Energy Agency, 2017).

However, only very few recent studies focus on the grid impacts of full-sized transit e-buses that charge in the urban low-voltage (LV)- or medium-voltage (MV) grid. Nevertheless, two relevant publications can be found in literature:

Rogge et al., 2015, analyzed the bus electrification capacity of a German city. The authors state that every second bus line could be electrified if buses charge their 220 kWh battery at every station with a charging power of 300 kW. However, the applied methodology does not include a validation based on grid simulations and only considers scenarios where buses charge at every station.

A grid simulation-based approach is pursued in Mohamed et al., 2017, where overnight charging is compared to charging at multiple stations. The results show that overnight charging is less problematic for the grid due to the lower charging power requirements. Charging at multiple stations thereby causes higher energy losses, voltage drops and frequent tap changing at the transformer stations. However, the applied simulation time steps of five minutes limit the resolution of the results. Hence, *Every Station Charging* scenarios cannot be evaluated with this approach.

In order to comprehensively assess all kinds of grid impacts of charging BEBs in urban environments, and to close the research gap of the missing comparisons between different charging patterns, a new approach has been developed and is presented in this work.

2. Methodology

In this paper, simulation-based grid impact assessments of high-power e-bus charging methods are performed on a typical urban European distribution grid. Parts of this work are conducted within the framework of the EU Horizon 2020 Project ASSURED, where charging power profiles of e-buses have been defined for the simulation scenarios. Based on these general assumptions, a large grid simulation is set up, and appropriate charging patterns of driving e-buses are modeled and aligned with the grid.

Fig. 1 Grid topology with MV charging stations marked in blue. The charging stations are located along the two MV feeders of the urban grid.

2.1. Grid

The grid used in the simulations for this paper was developed in the scope of the project DeCAS and is published in the European Union H2020 Project INTERPLAN. It is based on a comprehensive analysis of network data from four European countries and aims to represent a typical European distribution grid. Multiple network levels ranging from 0.4 kV up to 220 kV are modeled. The urban part of the grid is modified for this work by duplicating the urban feeders and the corresponding grid elements, and by adjusting the line length between the nodes where Electric Vehicle Supply Equipments (EVSEs) are located. The profile data such as load profiles, photovoltaic profiles (disabled by default) and distributed generation profiles are based on measurement data of existing systems with 15-minute intervals. To increase the time resolution of the simulation to 1 second, the data were scaled and polynomial interpolated. The 270 load elements of the urban distribution grid depicted at the bottom of Fig. 1 consist of 70 % apartment buildings and of 30 % industry and businesses. The blue markers highlight the 20 MV charging stations for the electric buses, located along the two urban 20 kV MV feeders of the grid. At the top left of Fig. 1, the meshed HV grid is located with active tap changers at the two 110/20 kV transformers, both having a rated power of approx. 30 MVA. The tap changers have a voltage set point of 1.03 per unit (p.u.), a lower switching bound of 1.02 p.u. and an upper bound of 1.05 p.u. The top right part of the figure shows that a rural MV and LV grid are also simulated in parallel. Nevertheless, the focus of this paper is on the urban distribution grid.

2.2. Modeling of Mobility Behavior and Charging

As an assumption for the mobility behavior of the e-buses, data from the Vienna Bus Network are used (Wiener Linien, 2017). There, the average driving speed of buses is 17.7 km/h and the average driving distance between two bus stops is 400 m. For the mobility scenario, a fully modeled electrified bus line roughly follows the path of the 20 MV EVSEs. In the grid model, the direct distance between two neighboring MV EVSEs is set to 250 m. Five additional electrified bus lines with a similar mobility pattern are assumed to end at different stations of the fully modeled line. This means that at five of the modeled EVSEs, an additional charging station is drawing charging power from the same grid node. In this manner, a total of six electrified bus lines can be simulated to load the urban MV grid.

Based on the results obtained in Gao et al., 2017, the energy consumption of the buses is set to 1.86 kWh/km, which corresponds to a consumption of buses with average battery sizes. Assuming the given driving speed and bus intervals of 10 minutes for the fully simulated 7600 m bus route, the number of simultaneously operating BEBs along the route is 8. Both driving directions have been taken into account for this calculation.

The charging behavior for *Every Station Charging* and *End Station Charging* is simulated as a linear charging model. The charging power is kept constant except of the first three seconds and the last 2 seconds of the charging event, where the power ramps up or down, respectively. The duration of a specific charging event varies from a few seconds to several minutes, depending on the set charging power and the chosen scenario. It is assumed that the buses continually recharge the same amount of energy which they consume during a full round trip. Therefore, the battery size of the buses is no constraint in this simulation approach.

Overnight Charging is also modeled, which involves a charging depot located at the leftmost charging station in Fig. 1 where all buses arrive after the end of business hours. During the night hours, the buses charge with two different power management schemes. One is peak shaving which limits the summed charging power of all buses to 600 kW. The other strategy involves only three charging spots – each being limited to 300 kW – at the depot. In contrast to *Every Station Charging* and *End Station Charging*, the charging behavior for *Overnight Charging* was modeled via a precise electric vehicle simulation model developed at AIT (Stahleder et al., 2018). By using this method, both the constant current- (CC) and the constant voltage- (CV) phase of charging are simulated and a battery size of roughly 700 kWh per bus is also considered.

Due to the lack of relevant high-power bus charger analyses in literature, no reasonable assertions regarding the characteristics of the simulated reactive power can be made. Hence the reactive power of the charging buses is set to zero for all simulations, which still gives a valuable estimation of the possible large-scale grid impacts of charging BEBs.

2.3. Simulation Scenarios

Grid impacts of the three already mentioned charging patterns *Every Station Charging*, *End Station Charging* and *Overnight Charging* are discussed in this work. This is done by performing and comparing grid simulations which all cover one full work day but are executed under different conditions. These are:

- Defined maximum charging power of 300 kW vs. 600 kW (in accordance with the scenario definition from the ASSURED project)
- Summer and winter scenarios are executed, with the winter scenarios being more energy intensive regarding the required charging capacity. This is due to bus interior heating during winter and is reflected

Fig. 2 Summed charging powers at the MV Feeder 1 for summer and winter. (a) Every Station Charging; (b) End Station Charging

in the simulations by increasing the BEB energy consumption by 10 % (see also Graurs et al., 2015). This results in longer charging durations at the EVSEs.

- PV is enabled for some scenarios. In these scenarios, 40 % of the grid connection points containing households are equipped with a PV system. The rated peak power of each PV system is set to 30 % of the peak power consumption of the corresponding households which occurred during a full year.

3. Results

The results of the performed grid simulations are presented in this section, with the focus on the chronological evolution of the grid parameters: node voltage, transformer loading and line loading. In all figures of this section only the 600 kW scenarios are plotted because they represent the worst-case situation. If significant differences exist between the 300 kW and the 600 kW results, it is separately mentioned in the text.

To get an overview of the BEB charging profiles, Fig. 2 (a) and (b) depict the cumulated power of all MV EVSEs at the left MV feeder in Fig. 1 for two different seasons. Fig. 2 (a) shows that for *Every Station Charging* scenarios, the increased energy consumption of the buses in winter results in a slightly higher simultaneity of charging than in summer.

In contrast, this effect is hardly visible for *End Station Charging* scenarios of Fig. 2 (b), where a lower count of longer charging events generates less overlaps in both seasons. More specifically, only a maximum of two charging processes happen simultaneously (1.2 MW), although four of the six simulated e-bus lines charge along this feeder. In comparison, the maximum charging power in Fig. 2 (a) amounts 2.4 MW.

The simulation results for two different 600 kW *Every Station Charging* scenarios are presented in Fig. 3. The first graph shows the loading of the main cable of the left urban MV feeder in Fig. 1. The middle and the bottom of the figure show the HV/MV transformer loading and the voltage of a peripheral MV node of the same feeder. The base grid load is higher in the winter scenario but is still uncritical with respect to these three parameters. The slightly increased energy demand of the buses in winter also does not cause any problems. The simulated grid seems to be well dimensioned for MV BEB charging.

Fig. 3 Every Station Charging with 600 kW: Summer vs. winter

Fig. 4 End Station Charging with 600 kW: Summer vs. winter

Fig. 5 Overnight Charging (Depot Charging) with two different strategies: Summer vs. winter

Fig. 6 End Station Charging with and without PV: Summer vs. winter

A similar situation is found in Fig. 4 which depicts the same comparison for the *End Station Charging* scenarios. The steadier periodicity of *End Station Charging* means a better predictability for grid operators. Also, the magnitude of the loading spikes and voltage drops due to a varying charging power is smaller than for *Every Station Charging*. This helps to reduce the tap changing frequency and, in turn, increases the transformer life time. In all executed simulations however, tap changing was not encountered because the MV voltage profiles at the substations stay within the voltage bounds of the transformers.

Interestingly, the winter scenario has a much higher base grid load than the summer scenario in the early evening. Furthermore, the peak load times – mainly caused by households – occur later in summer, which is plausible since the sunset also happens later in this season.

It should be noted that due to the polynomial interpolation of the load- and PV-profiles to a one second resolution, the base load profiles are probably smoother than real measurements (despite adding artificial noise). This also leads to smooth base grid parameters, which is evident when looking at the night hours between 00:00 and 06:00 in Fig. 3 and Fig. 4.

The next results which are shown in Fig. 5 are the two different *Overnight Charging* scenarios where the eight buses of one bus line charge in a large parking depot. The other bus lines are not considered in this approach. The difference between the two charging strategies is clearly visible in the top graph of the figure: While the *Peak Shave* algorithm limits the total charging power of all buses to 600 kW, the *3 EVSE @ 300 kW* strategy is limited to 900 kW. One can see that the constant-voltage (CV) phase of Li-Ion battery charging is also simulated. For the *Peak Shave* scenario, this phase of charging becomes relevant only in the right part of the figure because the batteries of the buses reach this critical state of charge at the same time. In comparison, the *3 EVSE @ 300 kW* scenario allows three buses to charge with a higher charging power. Hence, the CV phases of charging occur earlier in time. For both strategies it is evident that the winter scenarios take more time to fill the bus batteries than the

corresponding summer scenarios.

The grid impacts of the *Overnight Charging* approaches are relatively low in comparison to the other scenarios. There are three reasons for this: First, the base load of the grid is far lower in the night hours, which can be taken advantage of. Second, by continuously charging the batteries without interruptions due to driving, the summed power is lower than in *Every Station Charging* and *End Station Charging*. Third, the charging depot is located at a central MV node which reduces losses and helps to stabilize the line voltages.

A comparison of *End Station Charging* with and without activated PV systems is shown in Fig. 6 for both summer and winter seasons. Since the residential PV systems are mainly located in the low voltage grid, a close look is also taken at a peripheral LV node. The figure shows that in winter, PV has almost no impact on the node voltages and the transformer loading. However, in summer, the LV voltage profiles are higher if PV is enabled.

Another interesting fact in Fig. 6 is that the peripheral LV node is hardly influenced by the charging buses in the MV grid. This is good for residential customers because it indicates a stable voltage profile despite the charging buses.

4. Discussion

The results presented in this contribution provide an impact assessment of collective e-bus charging on typical urban distribution grids in Europe. The three different charging scenarios *Every Station Charging*, *End Station Charging* and *Overnight Charging* are compared with respect to different grid parameters.

Due to the lower simultaneity of charging processes, the *End Station Charging* scenarios prove to be more grid-friendly than *Every Station Charging*. The maximum summed charging power at one of the two main MV feeders is 2.4 MW in *Every Station Charging* and 1.2 MW in *End Station Charging*. Since the simulated urban grid is well dimensioned for high loads, the differences in the grid impacts are rather small. Nevertheless, *End Station Charging* proves to provide a slightly higher voltage stability and keeps the transformer power at a lower level. In weaker utility grids this difference could be crucial.

The *Overnight Charging* scenario cannot be directly compared with the other two approaches because only one bus line with 8 buses was considered in the depot. Still, this solution has several advantages, such as an optimal power management, a very high level of predictability and the option for a grid-friendly placement of the charging depot. However, very large battery sizes are required, which results in higher acquisition costs for the buses.

From the operation and financial point of view, no detailed analyses have been performed in this work. Several claims can still be made. *Every Station Charging* probably requires very high investment costs for charging infrastructure. Due to the smaller short-range batteries which would be used in this approach, some operation restrictions could arise, e.g. if the bus route must be changed to a different path. However, the battery costs would be lower than in all the other scenarios.

In comparison to *Overnight Charging*, the *End Station Charging* scenario has the advantage of a smaller and cheaper battery while keeping the infrastructure costs in an acceptable range. In some situations, operation restrictions could arise when buses must wait at the end station until their battery is recharged. However, the waiting time in the simulations performed in this work was lower than 3 minutes when charging with 600 kW and lower than 6 minutes in the case of 300 kW.

Although the grid model utilized in the simulations is based on a comprehensive study about typical European distribution grids, it should be noted that it is generic and does not exist in reality. When using other grid models, the simulation results could significantly differ from the ones obtained in this work. Nevertheless, this paper can be considered as a well-founded starting point for utility operators and city bodies who aim for an electrification of public road transport.

5. Conclusion

This work presents a simulation study about the electrification of urban distribution grids by comparing the grid impacts of different e-bus charging scenarios. These are *Every Station Charging*, *End Station Charging* and

Overnight Charging. From the grid perspective, the *End Station Charging* and *Overnight Charging* scenarios can be considered as favorable because they cause a lower maximum charging power and provide a better predictability of charging processes. Overnight charging, however, requires very large e-bus batteries which can be a limiting cost- and environment-factor.

In contrast to the few other studies about the grid integration of electric buses, this work enables precise comparisons of all kinds of different charging strategies. This is mainly due to the high time resolution of the simulations and the inclusion of a flexible simulation environment which involves an assessment of different seasons.

Future work will include simulations of various other distribution grids and will integrate reactive charging power profiles based on measurements of fast EVSEs. Furthermore, harmonic analyses of the grid will be performed.

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